

SEMI-CENTENNIAL OF THE BASIC STRUCTURE DOCTRINE: REVISITING THE *KESAVANAND BHARATI* JUDGMENT

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India's founding fathers and mothers established in the Constitution both the nation's ideals and the institutions and processes for achieving them. The ideals were national unity and integrity, and a democratic and equitable society. The new society was to be achieved through a social-economic revolution pursued with a democratic spirit using constitutional, democratic institutions. I later came to think of unity, social revolution, and democracy as three strands of a seamless web. The founders believed that none of these goals was to be pursued, nor could any be achieved separately. They were mutually dependent and had to be sought together.'

- Granville Austin.¹

ABSTRACT: The 'doctrine of basic structure' is one of the most pivotal principles of India's constitutional law. Fifty years ago, in 1973, the Supreme Court of India propounded this doctrine in its landmark Judgment in *Kesavananda Bharati v. State of Kerala*. This doctrine imposes implied limits on the Parliament's 'constitution-amending power' given under Art. 368 of the Constitution. Since 1973, this doctrine has guided constitutional practice in the country and helped safeguard the fundamental values of democracy. It has played a significant role in maintaining the integrity and stability of the nation's legal framework, ensuring that the core principles of the Constitution remain protected and consistent. The present paper revisits the origin of this doctrine and its subsequent development. It also analyses the consolidation and the relevance of the basic structure doctrine. It also examines whether the judiciary

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¹ Granville Austin, *The Indian Constitution: Cornerstone of a Nation*, Preface to the OIP edn.1999 (OUP, 1966), p xi

is overstepping its bounds by restricting the legislature's constituent power, or performing its constitutional obligation to protect the Constitution?

KEYWORDS: Sovereign, Democratic Republic, Fundamental Values, Constitutional Governance, Basic Structure Doctrine

I. INTRODUCTION

The Constitution is a document that provides a framework within which a government operates. The government is itself divided into major organs or institutions. Broadly speaking, these are the Legislative, Executive, and Judicial branches. It is believed that the governing function comprises the making of laws, the execution of laws, the interpretation of laws, and the settlement of disputes.² These organs function under the mandate of the constitutional provisions. The Constitution of India is described as the world's detailed written constitution, having a unique national character that reflects India's diversity. It contains salient features such as a federal structure, fundamental rights and their enforcement, the role and powers of the constitutional authorities, separation of powers, a democratic form of government, an independent judiciary, the rule of law, a unique blend of rigidity and flexibility and most importantly, an oath to uphold the Constitution. The Indian Constitution reflects a commitment to justice, liberty, and equality, enduring fundamental rights. The Constitution is a selection of the legal rules, embodied in a document, to guide the government. To address the needs of a constantly evolving society, the Founding Fathers envisioned a balance between flexibility and rigidity in the Constitution⁴. Art. 368 of the Constitution is visualised within that vision, which permits the Legislature to amend the provisions of the Constitution.⁵

2 Uday Raj Rai, *Constitutional Law: Governance Structure*, 2nd edn., Eastern Book Company (2022), p 563

3 K. C. Wheare, *Modern Constitutions*, 1st edn. OUP, (1951), p 2

4 *Supra* Note 2, p 564, like every other branch of law, constitutional law must mirror the socio-economic realities of the country at the time of its adoption, while also accommodating the prevailing political balance of forces. Since, social and political conditions are never static and equilibrium is frequently disturbed, constitutional change becomes inevitable. Law, by its nature, often trails behind the facts of life; yet when the gap between legal provisions and ground realities grows too wide and crosses the threshold of tolerance, the law is either swept aside or faces open defiance

5 Chapter 20 of the Constitution of India, is titled "*Amendment of the Constitution.*" It contains only one Art. *i. e.* Art. 368, which deals with 'the Power of Parliament to amend the Constitution and procedure therefor', to be followed for such amendment. Art. 368 represents not only the procedure of amendment but also ensures a balance of powers between the Union and the States by mandating their participation in altering matters of common concern, as amended by the Constitution (Twenty-fourth Amendment) Act, 1971

The Constitution is not an ordinary law; it is the supreme and fundamental law from which all other statutes and governmental institutions derive their legitimacy. The Legislature, the Executive, the Judiciary and other authorities owe their existence to the Constitution, and all are under an obligation to act within the constitutional framework. The Constitution inspires reverence in the collective consciousness of the people. The essential characteristics of the Constitution would be undermined if the legislature frequently alters the power-limiting provisions. If constitutional amendments occur too often without restraint, the supreme law of the land loses its sanctity, which may cause irreparable harm to the public psyche and thereby diminish the legacy of the Constitution.

Since 1950, in the first two decades of constitutional practice in India, the amending power of Parliament was understood to be plenary and unrestricted. Consequently, it led to frequent constitutional amendments that altered the scope of property rights, land reforms, and socio-economic policies.⁶ Subsequently, a gradual conflict arose between the Parliament and the Supreme Court. Parliament, through its amending power, asserted its supremacy, and called into question the role of the judiciary, which is under a constitutional obligation to protect the Constitution and the fundamental rights of individuals.⁷ Thus, it became inevitable to maintain a reasonable balance between the powers of the two organs of the State and to resolve such conflicts. Later, it culminated in the propounding of the 'basic structure doctrine.' It was a purely judicial innovation that established the supremacy of the Constitution over all the transient political majorities.⁸

At the end of seventy-five years of the Indian Constitution's journey, the 'basic structure doctrine' has evolved beyond a mere judicial innovation; it now stands as an integral component of India's constitutional culture. It has preserved the Constitution's identity through many turbulent phases: the era of National Emergency from 1975 to 1977; one-party dominance; later coalition politics, including a hung Parliament; and other contemporary challenges, such as populism and majoritarianism. A few questions can naturally arise in the minds of ordinary citizens: Does a constitutional amendment aim to ensure justice, liberty, equality, and fraternity by upholding these democratic values and

6 1950 to 1970 nearly thirty constitutional amendments were made to the newly adopted Constitution during the period.

7 See Art 32 of the Constitution of India

8 H.M. Seervai, *Constitutional Law of India*, Vol. III (4th edn., Universal Law Publishing, 2013) p300+

maintaining the country's democratic order? Or does it undermine the core values of the Constitution and destroy them? It seems that these fundamental and common questions were before the higher courts, which motivated the evolution of the 'Basic Structure Doctrine.'

II. GENESIS OF THE BASIC STRUCTURE DOCTRINE: AN OVERVIEW

The 'basic structure doctrine,' which consists of three words, was evolved to safeguard and preserve the Constitution of India as the founding fathers intended. The doctrine states that even Constitutional amendments are open to judicial review on substantive grounds if an amendment is made which destroys what the Court decides is the 'basic structure' of the Constitution. Therefore, the genesis of the 'basic structure doctrine' can be traced to the early constitutional disputes over Parliament's power to amend the Constitution.⁹ Since the concept of the basic structure begins with Art. 368 of the Constitution, a review of the models that preceded the Constituent Assembly (which explain how this article ultimately emerged), reveals that it was incorporated for two reasons. The first is that the power to amend or change a Constitution is one of the most important provisions that a flexible document like a Constitution must contain, for such a provision is essential if it is to reflect the felt needs of the times ultimately. Secondly, the language of Article 368 is of little important. As it originally stood, it used two words: in the first part of the article, the word 'amend' is used, and in the second part (proviso), the word 'change' is used. What does it

⁹ The origin of the doctrine can be traced back to the land reforms law that were introduced in the Indian State of Kerala in the 1950s and 1960s. These reforms aimed to redistribute land from large landowners to the landless and the poor. In 1963, the Kerala government enacted the Kerala Land Reforms Act, which imposed a limit on the amount of land that an individual could own. The Act provided for the acquisition of excess land from landowners and its distribution to the landless and the poor. Sri Kesavananda Bharati was the head (pontiff) of the Edneer Muth, a Hindu religious institution in Kerala, India. In 1970, the Government of Kerala imposed restrictions on the ownership of land held by religious institutions. The Edneer Muth, headed by Sri Kesavananda Bharati, challenged the constitutionality of the Act in the Kerala High Court. The case eventually reached the Supreme Court, which ruled in favour of the state government. The Parliament of India, in the meantime, passed the 24th Amendment to the Constitution, which sought to curtail the judiciary's powers and limit the scope of judicial review. The 25th and 29th Amendments were also passed, seeking to limit citizens' fundamental rights and to grant Parliament the power to amend any part of the Constitution. Sri Kesavananda Bharati filed a petition challenging the validity of these amendments, arguing that they violated the basic structure of the Constitution. This led to the landmark Kesavananda Bharati judgment, which gave rise to the basic structure doctrine and placed limits on Parliament's power to amend the Constitution. The case became one of the most important cases in Indian constitutional history, and Sri Kesavananda Bharati is remembered as a key figure in the fight to uphold the principles of democracy and the rule of law in India (<https://judgments.ecourts.gov.in/>, last visited on 01.12.2024)

mean? It means that if any amendment or change is made, the Constitution shall stand amended; if it stands amended, obviously, the Constitution, as a Constitution, must remain.

However, there is another view regarding the theory of its evolution. It is noteworthy to mention here that in February 1965, the Law College of Banaras Hindu University had invited a distinguished German constitutional law jurist, Dietrich Conrad, Professor at the South Asia Institute of the University of Heidelberg, Germany, to deliver a lecture on the topic, *‘Implied Limitation of the Amending Power of Parliament’* in the context of the Indian Constitution. It has, since, been widely acknowledged that Prof. (Dr) D. Conrad’s formulation had laid down the foundation of what later came to be known as the ‘Basic Structure Doctrine’. In his lecture, he explained that the misuse of the Weimar Constitution (Germany’s constitution from 1919 to 1949) by Adolf Hitler during the Nazi era had a significant impact on him, and that he drew upon Germany’s constitutional experience during that period to develop his ‘theory of implied limitations’. He opined that:

‘It is hardly possible to restrict the legal meaning of amendment to improvement, nor can it be denied that by amendment, complete Articles may be removed or replaced.’¹⁰

He argued that an amending body, no matter how powerful, cannot alter the very structure that underpins its constitutional authority. In other words, an amending body (i.e., the legislature) cannot modify the Constitution and its provisions that grant it the power of amendment in the first place. There are certain implied limitations on an amending body, under which specific areas or principles in the Constitution are beyond its reach. Finally, this was known as the ‘Doctrine of Limitation’¹¹.

Further, Prof. Conrad turned to Art. 368 of the Constitution of India, which provides that the Parliament may amend the Constitution, provided that the Amendment Bill is passed in each House by a majority of the total membership of that House present and voting. But he posed several hypotheticals, such as: Could Parliament, by exercising its powers under Art. 368, amend Art. 1? and divide the Union of India into ‘Tamil Nadu’ and ‘Hindustan proper’? Could it abolish ‘the Right to Life and Personal Liberty’ guaranteed under Art. 21? If a ruling party, faced with a declining majority, sought to amend Art. 368 to vest all power in the President acting on the advice of the Prime Minister, would

10 Cited in AIR 1973 SC 1457 at 2023

11 Ibid

such an amendment be valid? Could the amending power be stretched to abolish the Constitution itself and restore monarchy? He unequivocally replied no, arguing that such sweeping changes would subvert the very ethos of the sovereign, democratic republic of India, erode the constitutional order, and transform the country's system of governance into a dictatorship. Hence, he submitted that there is a need for implied limitations in every Constitution. The term "amend" does not mean changing the entire Constitution.

This academic discourse, eight years before the *Kesavananda Bharati* judgment, advanced the proposition that Parliament's power to amend the Constitution is not absolute but constrained by the Constitution's basic features (structure). The democratic values that the framers of the Constitution of India consciously embedded in it cannot be entirely altered.

III. THE BASIC STRUCTURE DOCTRINE: A JUDICIAL INNOVATION

The basic structure doctrine emerged partly as a result of constitutional amendments of the early years of independence and partly from judicial decisions. Since the dawn of independence, with the enforcement of the Constitution, a gradual conflict arose primarily over the right to property and the extent to which socio-economic reforms could be insulated from judicial review. The Supreme Court came across various cases during this period.¹² However, the signs of a few foundational features of the Constitution were highlighted in *Sajjan Singh v. State of Rajasthan* in both Judgments¹³, and in *Golak Nath v. State of Punjab*. Where one of the most significant arguments advanced was that Parliament's power to amend the Constitution is not unlimited but is subject to inherent restrictions implied in Art. 368 itself. This reasoning suggested that certain features of the Constitution could not be amended or destroyed through the amending process. Although not fully crystallised at that time, this line of thought subsequently provided a conceptual foundation for the 'Basic Structure Doctrine' as articulated in *Kesavananda Bharati v. State of Kerala*.¹⁴

12 *Chiranjit Lal v. Union of India*, AIR 1951 SC 41; *State of Bihar v. Maharajahdiraja Sir Kameshwar Singh*, AIR 1952 SC 252; *Dwarika Das Srinwas v. Sholapur Spg. and Wvg. Co. Ltd.*, AIR 1954 SC 112; *Commr. Hindu Religious Endowment v. Swamiar*, AIR 1954 SC 282; *State of West Bengal v. Mrs. Bella Banerjee*, AIR 1954 SC 170; *Bombay Dying Co. v. State of Bombay*, AIR 1958 SC 328; *R.C. Cooper v. Union of India*, AIR 1970 SC 564 (*Bank Nationalisation Case*); *Deokinandan Prasad v. State of Bihar*, AIR 1971 SC 328

13 AIR 1965 SC 845 and AIR 1967 SC 1643

14 (1973) 4 SCC 225

The Constitution (First Amendment) Act, 1951, inserted Arts. 31A and 31B into the Constitution to protect agrarian reform laws from challenges on the ground that they violated the fundamental right to property under Art. 31. Though in the case of *Shankari Prasad Singh Deo v. Union of India*,¹⁵ the Supreme Court upheld the validity of the amendment, holding that the power to amend under Art. 368 of the Constitution extends to the Fundamental Rights. The Court reasoned that “law” in Art. 13 did not include a constitutional amendment. This judgment indirectly established Parliament’s monopoly over constitutional amendments. The Court held that:

‘the power given under Art. 368 for amendment is not an ordinary legislative power but a constituent power, and therefore its exercise does not fall within the scope of Art. 13(2). ———

_____’¹⁶

Thus, the Supreme Court has held that the limitation placed upon ordinary legislative power by Art. 13(2) does not apply to the power of amending the Constitution under Art. 368. By exercising this power, Part III of the Constitution can be amended, and the amendment cannot be invalid merely on the ground that it takes away or abridges any fundamental right. The Supreme Court, in its decision, held that Art. 13(2) and Art. 368 are entirely independent of each other. Therefore, according to this reasoning, Art. 368 must be read by excluding Art. 13(2) from its ambit.¹⁷

A decade later, the Constitution (Seventeenth Amendment) Act, 1964, was challenged in *Sajjan Singh v. State of Rajasthan*.¹⁸ By a majority, the Supreme Court reiterated that Parliament possessed unrestricted amending power. However, the dissenting opinions of Mudholkar and Hidayatullah, JJ., questioned whether this power was inherently limited. Mudholkar, J, has observed that the Constitution had a “basic structure” that could not be abrogated, foreshadowing the doctrine later crystallised in *Kesavananda Bharati*. In *Sajjan Singh v. State of Rajasthan*¹⁹, M. Hidayatullah and Mudholkar, JJ., in their minority opinions, observed that Fundamental Rights form an inseparable and integral part of the Constitution of India. They emphasised in dissent that these rights constitute

15 AIR 1951 SC 458

16 Ibid

17 (1951) FCC 966, para 15 at 984

18 AIR 1965 SC 845

19 Ibid

essential elements of the constitutional framework and, as the basic rights of human beings, lie beyond Parliament's amending power and therefore cannot be amended. Thus, the earliest signs of the origin of the 'Basic Structure Doctrine' can be seen in the minority opinion given in the judgment of the *Sajjan Singh case*²⁰, and became clearly visible in later Judgments.

The turning point came in *I.C. Golak Nath v. State of Punjab*,²¹ in which, by a narrow majority (6:5), the Supreme Court held that Parliament could not amend Fundamental Rights. The majority invoked Art. 13, holding that a constitutional amendment was "law" and could, therefore, be struck down if it violated Fundamental Rights. The judgment virtually froze Parliament's power to alter Part III. The political response was swift: Parliament passed the Constitution (Twenty-Fourth Amendment) Act, 1971, expressly affirming its power to amend any part of the Constitution, including Fundamental Rights.

20 As per Mudholkar J., it is true that the Constitution does not directly prohibit the amendment of Part III. But it would indeed be strange that rights which are considered to be fundamental, and which include one which is guaranteed by the Constitution (*vide* Art. 32), should be more easily capable of being abridged or restricted than any of the matters referred to in the proviso to Art. 368, some of which are perhaps less vital than fundamental rights. It is possible, as suggested by my learned brother, that Art. 368 merely lays down the procedure to be followed for amending the Constitution and does not confer a power to amend the Constitution which, I think, has to be ascertained from the provision sought to be amended or other relevant provisions or the Preamble. The argument that if fundamental rights are regarded as unchangeable, it will hamper legislation which the changing needs of a dynamic society may call for in the future, is weighty enough and merits consideration. It is possible that there may be an answer. The rights enumerated in Art. 19(1) can be subjected to reasonable restrictions under clauses (2) to (6) of Art. 19, and the other fundamental rights—or at least many of them—can perhaps be adapted to meet the needs of a changing society with the aid of the directive principles. For Art. 37, the second Art. in Part IV which deals with "Directive Principles of State Policy," imposes a duty on the State to apply those directive principles in making laws. These principles are also fundamental in the governance of the country, and the provisions of Part III of the Constitution must be interpreted harmoniously with those principles. This is also an aspect of the matter which requires consideration. He further, observed that: We may also have to bear in mind the fact that ours is a written Constitution. The Constituent Assembly, which was the repository of sovereignty, could well have created a sovereign Parliament on the British model. But instead it enacted a written Constitution, created three organs of State, made the Union executive responsible to Parliament and the State executives to the State legislatures, erected a federal structure and distributed legislative power between Parliament and the State legislatures; recognised certain rights as fundamental and provided for their enforcement; prescribed forms of oaths of office or affirmations which require those who subscribe to them to owe true allegiance to the Constitution, and further require the members of the Union Judiciary and of the higher judiciary in the States to uphold the Constitution. Above all, it formulated a solemn and dignified Preamble which appears to be an epitome of the basic features of the Constitution. Can it not be said that these are indicia of the intention of the Constituent Assembly to give permanency to the basic features of the Constitution?

21 AIR 1967 SC 1643

This legislative assertion again set the stage for the epic confrontation in *Kesavananda Bharati*.

a) *Kesavananda Bharati* Case: The Watershed

The decision in *Kesavananda Bharati v. State of Kerala*²², is widely regarded as the most significant constitutional judgment in the history of Indian constitutional law. The largest-ever bench decided this case and thereby settled the debate on the scope of Parliament's constitution-amending power under Art. 368, though in a manner that was neither unanimous nor uncontroversial.²³

Thus, this case gave rise to a confrontation between Parliament's claim of unlimited constituent power and the judiciary's duty to safeguard the Constitution's identity. The Supreme Court constituted a thirteen-judge bench, the largest in its history and on 24 April 1973, by a slender majority of 7:6, held that while Parliament has broad powers to amend the Constitution, it cannot alter its 'basic structure.'

S. M. Sikri, CJ, announced that certain essential features, such as the supremacy of the Constitution, democracy, parliamentary form of government, secularism, separation of powers, and federalism, formed part of the basic structure and are beyond the reach of Parliament.²⁴ Sikri, CJ (for the majority), propounded that the Constitution has certain fundamental features which cannot be abrogated. H.R. Khanna, J, delivered the crucial swing vote, holding that Parliament's amending power is not unlimited. He emphasised that the Constitution, unlike an ordinary statute, has a higher norm that preserves its identity. A.N. Ray, J, and minority judges argued for unfettered amending power, emphasising parliamentary sovereignty. The opinions were fragmented, but the common thread in the majority was recognition of implied limitations on Art. 368 of the Constitution.

The judgment validated the Constitution (Twenty-Fourth Amendment) Act, *i.e.*, and Parliament's power to amend, but read into Art. 368 an unwritten limitation. Parliament could amend, but not destroy or emasculate the Constitution's essential features. The political reaction was hostile, as evidenced

22 (1973) 4 SCC 225

23 Swami Kesavananda Bharati, the head of a religious *Muth* in Kerala, challenged the Kerala Land Reforms Act, 1969, which sought to impose restrictions on the management of property belonging to religious institutions. The challenge soon expanded beyond property rights to question the constitutional validity of the Constitution (24th, 25th, 26th, and 29th Amendments) Act. Parliament passed these constitutional amendments in response to the *Golak Nath* judgment to reassert its authority to amend Fundamental Rights.

24 S.M. Sikri, CJ, majority opinion in *Kesavananda Bharati*, *Ibid*

by the appointment of the then Chief Justice of India²⁵. Upendra Baxi, a known scholar of Constitutional Law, has observed that the *Kesavananda Bharati* judgment transformed Indian constitutionalism from a 'text-bound structure' into a 'culture of constitutionalism' where values, not words alone, guide interpretation.²⁶

b) Expansion and Consolidation of the Doctrine

The doctrine laid down in *Kesavananda Bharati* did not remain static. Over the decades, the Supreme Court has applied and expanded it across diverse contexts, clarifying the contours of the 'basic structure doctrine.' In the aftermath of the Allahabad High Court's judgment setting aside the then Prime Minister of India, Mrs Indira Gandhi's election for electoral malpractices, Parliament again sought to immunise the Prime Minister's election from judicial scrutiny through the Constitution (Thirty-Ninth Amendment) Act, 1975. In *Indira Nehru Gandhi v. Sri Raj Narain and Anr*,²⁷ the Supreme Court struck down this amendment, holding that free and fair elections are an essential feature of democracy and therefore part of the basic structure. This decision reaffirmed that Parliament's power to amend could not be used to tilt the balance of democratic processes in favour of incumbents.

The Constitution (Forty-Second Amendment) Act, 1976, was passed during the Emergency, sought to expand Parliament's amending power by excluding judicial review and declaring the primacy of the Directive Principles over Fundamental Rights. In *Minerva Mills v. Union of India*,²⁸ the Supreme Court held that Sections 4 and 55 of the Constitution (Forty-Second Amendment) Act, 1976, were invalid, ruling that the limited amending power itself forms part of the basic structure. It also restored the balance between Fundamental Rights and Directive Principles, holding that both are essential for constitutional harmony.

In *Waman Rao v. Union of India*,²⁹ the Supreme Court held that constitutional amendments made before *Kesavananda Bharati* (24 April 1973)

25 By superseding the three senior-most judges (Shehlat, Grover, Hegde JJ.) of the Supreme Court, Justice A.N. Ray was appointed as the Chief Justice of India, which affected the constitutional practice in such appointment. This marked the beginning of a tense and confrontational phase in judicial-executive relations.

26 Upendra Baxi, *The Indian Supreme Court and Politics* (Eastern Book Company, 1980) p124

27 AIR 1975 SC 2299

28 (1980) 3 SCC 625

29 (1981) 2 SCC 362

could not be reviewed under the basic structure test. Still, amendments thereafter would be subject to scrutiny. This “prospective overruling” principle created legal certainty while preserving the authority of the *Kesavananda Bharati* case.

As it is well known, the Ninth Schedule, created by the First Amendment (1951), was designed to protect land reforms and other socio-economic legislations from judicial review. Over time, numerous laws were placed in the Ninth Schedule, often to shield them from constitutional challenges. In *I.R. Coelho v. State of Tamil Nadu*,³⁰ a nine-judge bench of the Supreme Court unanimously held that even laws placed in the Ninth Schedule, after 24 April 1973, are subject to judicial review if they violate the ‘basic structure principles’ of equality and the rule of law. This case reaffirmed the judiciary’s constitutional duty to protect fundamental rights from legislative insulation.

At the time of the Constitution (Ninety-Ninth Amendment) Act, 2014, the Act sought to replace the collegium system with the NJAC for judicial appointments to the higher judiciary. In *Supreme Court Advocates-on-Record Association v. Union of India*,³¹ a five-judge bench struck down the NJAC, holding that judicial primacy in appointments is part of the basic structure under the principle of judicial independence. This decision highlighted that the doctrine continues to evolve and safeguard institutional autonomy, even in the face of major constitutional reforms. In the Electoral Bond case,³² the Supreme Court recently held that:

‘the democratic set-up of Government is a part of the basic features of the Constitution. Elections matter in a democracy. They are the most profound expression of the will of the people. Our parliamentary democracy enables citizens to express their will through their elected representatives. The integrity of the electoral process is a necessary concomitant to the maintenance of the democratic form of Government.’³³

Consequently, the Court declared the ‘Electoral Bond Scheme’ unconstitutional and liable to be struck down, the proviso to Sec. 29-C (1) of the Representation of the People Act; the proviso to Sec. 182(3) of the Companies Act, 2013; and Sec. 13-A (b) of the Income Tax Act, 1961, as amended by

30 (2007) 2 SCC 1

31 (2015) 6 SCC 1

32 *Assn. for Democratic Reforms & Anr v. Union of India*, (2024) 5 SCC 1

33 *Id.*, para 208

the Finance Act, 2017. The Court further invalidated the deletion of the proviso to Sec. 182(1) of the Companies Act, 2013, which had permitted unlimited corporate funding of political parties. In addition, Sec. 31(3) of the Reserve Bank of India Act, 1934, along with the Explanation introduced by the Finance Act, 2017, was declared unconstitutional. The Court consequently prohibited the issuance of fresh electoral bonds³⁴.

Through these expansions³⁵ of the basic structure, the doctrine has grown from a judicial innovation into a fundamental element of Indian democracy, and Constitutional law constantly adapting to new constitutional challenges.

IV. THE BASIC STRUCTURE DOCTRINE: AN APPRAISAL

Although the basic structure doctrine is well-established in Indian constitutional law, it continues to face criticism. Legal scholars, jurists, and political leaders have questioned its legitimacy, democratic foundations, and lack of well-defined boundaries, resulting in extensive debate over its jurisprudential basis.

On the one hand, a common criticism is that the doctrine constitutes judicial overreach. Critics argue that the Constitution grants Parliament the power to amend under Art. 368, and that the judiciary has no authority to impose implied limits. By reading extra-textual constraints into the Constitution, the higher judiciary assumes the role of a 'super-legislature.' Seervai, a renowned constitutional law practitioner, did not welcome this formulation and remarked that it was an invention without a textual basis. He contended that it 'substitutes the wisdom of judges for the will of the people expressed through Parliament.'³⁶ The second point of criticism concerns the 'doctrine's indeterminacy'. The Court has never provided an exhaustive list of what constitutes the basic structure. Instead, it has identified features on a case-by-case basis. This ad hoc approach raises concerns about unpredictability. Legislators cannot be sure which amendment might later be struck down as violating the basic structure. Moreover, they argue that unelected judges should not have the final say over constitutional amendments passed by the elected legislature. They claim that the doctrine undermines parliamentary sovereignty and the popular will. According to this

34 Id, para 309

35 *P Sambamurthy v. State of Andhra Pradesh*, AIR 1987 SC 663; *L Chandra Kumar v. Union of India*, AIR 1997 SC 1125; *Indira Sawhney v Union of India*, AIR 1992 SC 477; *Dr Jaishri Laxanrao Patil v. The Chief Minister*, (2021) 8 SCC 1

36 *Supra* Note 8, Pp 3118-19

view, the doctrine creates a ‘counter-majoritarian difficulty’ in which a few judges can frustrate reforms endorsed by the majority.³⁷

On the other hand, defenders argue that the doctrine is essential to preserve constitutional identity. Without it, transient majorities could damage democracy itself, abolish judicial review, or subvert fundamental rights. As Upendra Baxi notes, the doctrine ensures that “the Constitution is not a plaything of political power but a living document anchored in justice.”³⁸ Comparative constitutional law also supports this doctrine.³⁹

Some scholars suggest that the doctrine is both necessary and problematic. It protects democracy, but must be applied cautiously. Judicial self-restraint is essential to avoid charges of arbitrariness. The doctrine’s legitimacy, therefore, lies not merely in theory but in careful and principled application.

V. THE BASIC STRUCTURE DOCTRINE AND TODAY’S CHALLENGES TO INDIAN DEMOCRACY

The doctrine of basic structure, far from being a relic of the 1970s, has acquired renewed significance in the contemporary constitutional and political landscape. At the time of strong parliamentary majorities, and rising debates over constitutional values, the judiciary’s articulation of the doctrine acts as both a shield against authoritarian impulses and a sword for preserving democratic ideals. This doctrine, no doubt strengthens parliamentary democracy in India. and federalism, which is a core element of the basic structure, ensures the States’ autonomy within the Union.

In *S.R. Bommai v. Union of India*⁴⁰ and *Kuldip Nayar v. Union of India*⁴¹, the Supreme Court stressed that federalism is an integral part of India’s constitutional identity. Centralisation under strong government, the use of Art. 356 has strained the federal balance. The doctrine ensures that amendments or policies that undermine the State’s autonomy may be subject to constitutional scrutiny. Secularism is explicitly identified as part of the basic structure. In a deeply pluralistic society like India, secularism ensures equal treatment of all religions by the State. The Supreme Court has held that secularism is a

37 Aharon Barak, *The Judge in a Democracy* (Princeton University Press, 2006) p123

38 Upendra Baxi, *The Indian Supreme Court and Politics* (Eastern Book Company, 1980) p130

39 Germany’s “eternity clause” (Art. 79 (3) of the Basic Law) prohibits amendments that alter federalism, democracy, or fundamental rights

40 (1994) 3 SCC 1

41 AIR 2006 SC 3127

foundational principle. Misuse of state power to promote one religion is unconstitutional.⁴² So, secularism remains a living application of the doctrine.⁴³ Democracy requires free and fair elections. Judicial independence has emerged as a central element of the doctrine. In the NJAC Case, the Supreme Court struck down the Constitution (Ninety-Ninth Amendment) Act, 2014, and the NJAC Act, 2014, holding that judicial primacy in appointments is part of the basic structure.⁴⁴ The doctrine, therefore, functions as a safeguard against capture of the judiciary.

The most significant test of the doctrine today is the rise of common voices advocating the review of the Constitution. It increases the risk of constitutional redesign by political leaders. In today's context, the debates around the Uniform Civil Code (UCC) raise tensions between equality (Art. 14), religious freedom (Arts. 25–28), and the directive principle (Art. 44); socio-economic rights (right to education, right to livelihood, right to privacy) have been read into Part III, reflecting serious concerns. The doctrine ensures that neither individual rights nor socio-economic goals are sacrificed entirely. As India enters the next phase of its constitutional journey, new challenges, such as populism, communal polarisation, digital governance, and climate justice will test the resilience of its constitutional values. The 'doctrine of basic structure', if applied with judicial restraint and principled reasoning, will continue to serve as the moral compass of Indian democracy.

India's basic structure doctrine has, thus far, prevented its entire dismantling. In the Indian context, proposals for restructuring the general elections, federal finance, or constitutional changes could be subject to judicial review. While the doctrine safeguards democracy, its frequent invocation raises concerns of judicial autonomy. For instance, critics of the NJAC judgment argue that the Supreme Court insulated itself from reform under the cover of the basic structure doctrine. The doctrine thus faces the paradox of being both a guardian and a source of judicial excess.

However, after seventy-five years of constitutional practice, the doctrine has preserved the core values of democracy, secularism, federalism, and the rule of law; provided a counter-majoritarian check on transient political power; and inspired global constitutionalism, especially in South Asia. Yet, its future lies in

42 *Supra* Note 40

43 *Ibid*

44 *Supreme Court Advocates-On-Record Assn. v. Union of India*, (2015) 6 SCC 1

measured application. Judicial restraint and principled reasoning will be crucial to ensure that the doctrine remains a guardian of democracy rather than a source of judicial autocracy.

VI. THE BASIC STRUCTURE DOCTRINE: ITS TRANSCENDING INFLUENCE

The basic structure doctrine, which is of Indian origin, has transcended borders and inspired constitutional courts beyond India. This doctrine holds that certain constitutional fundamentals are immune to the amending power of the Legislature. This doctrine has influenced the constitutional frameworks of South Asian countries, which grapple with the tension between parliamentary sovereignty and constitutional supremacy.⁴⁵

In Bangladesh, in the case of *Anwar Hussain Chowdhry v. Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh*,⁴⁶ the Supreme Court of Bangladesh, by a 3:1 majority, struck down the impugned amendment to Art. 100, and the notifications on the ground that there is an implied limitation on the power to amend the Constitution. The Supreme Court of Bangladesh held that there is a distinction between legislative power and constituent power of the Legislature. In this context, the Eighth Amendment was struck down, which sought to establish permanent benches of the High Court in various regions of Bangladesh. The Bangladesh Apex Court has held that the amendment undermines judicial independence and violates the basic structure of the Constitution. The Court observed that:

‘The power to amend any provision of the Constitution by way of addition, alteration, substitution or repeal is found to be plenary —————. However, a built-in limitation in the word “amend” does not authorise the abrogation or destruction of the Constitution or any of its three structural pillars, which will render the Constitution defunct or unworkable.’⁴⁷

45 See Roznai, *Unconstitutional Constitutional Amendments* (n 1) Pp 49–52; Paula R Newberg, *Judging the State: Courts and Constitutional Politics in Pakistan* (CUP 1995) Pp 237–41, 243–44; Martin Lau, *The Role of Islam in the Legal System of Pakistan* (Brill 2006) Pp 81–88. For related work on the migration (and transformation) of constitutional ideas, see Michel Rosenfeld and András Sajó, ‘Spreading Liberal Constitutionalism: An Inquiry into the Fate of Free Speech Rights in New Democracies’ in Sujit Choudhry (ed), *The Migration of Constitutional Ideas* (CUP 2006) Pp 42

46 (1989) 41 DLR (ad) 165; 9 BCR (1989) (AD)1

47 Ibid

Thus, by the majority judgment, the Court allowed the appeal and the impugned order of the High Court's division was set aside. It has also been established that specific provisions of the Constitution, including democracy, Republican Government, a Unitary State, separation of powers, judicial independence, and fundamental rights, constitute the basic structures of the Constitution of Bangladesh. These structural pillars of the Constitution are protected from amendment. Henceforth, any amendment will be *ultra vires* if it weakens the judiciary by creating rival courts to the High Court division under the guise of permanent benches, granting them complete jurisdiction, power, and authority. Again, in *Kudrat-E-Elahi Panir v. Bangladesh*,⁴⁸ the Supreme Court reaffirmed that democracy, the rule of law, and the separation of powers are part of the Constitution's basic structure. Bangladesh, thus, judicially constitutionalised the doctrine, making it a permanent part of its constitutional law. Here, it is worth mentioning the observation of the Court:

‘That in dealing with Constitutional Provisions, the court is not allowed to take hypothetical questions. Abstract theoretical questions are not to be decided by any court, as they are of only academic importance. It is true that the fundamental principles of State Policy, as contained in our Constitution, have been declared fundamental to the governance of Bangladesh and shall be applied by the State in the making of laws. Still, we will normally hold that the State will not enact a law that is contrary to the fundamental principles of State Policy. However, even then, if a law is enacted by disregarding these fundamental principles of State policy, the Government will have to answer to and face the people who elected them. So, by taking a hypothetical question, and on an interpretation —
—————of the
Constitution in the face of a clear constitutional mandate.’⁴⁹

In Pakistan, the Supreme Court also gradually moved closer to this doctrine. In *State v. Zia-ur-Rehman*⁵⁰, the Supreme Court of Pakistan declined to adopt the ‘basic structure doctrine’, asserting the supremacy of Parliament. However, in this case, Hamoodur Rahman C.J., on the point of the ‘basic structure doctrine’, has observed that:

48 (1992) 44 DLR (AD) 319, 44 DLR(AD) (1992) 319

49 Ibid

50 (PLD 1973 SC 49)

‘This does not say that the Objectives Resolution is the grundnorm, but that the grundnorm is the doctrine of legal sovereignty accepted by the people of Pakistan and the consequences that flow from it. I did not describe the ‘Objectives Resolution’ as the cornerstone of Pakistan’s legal edifice, but merely pointed out that one of the learned counsel appearing in the case had described it as such.’⁵¹

The Pakistan Supreme Court in the case of Zia-ur-Rehman has, however, firmly supported the principle that a Constitutional provision cannot be challenged on the ground of being repugnant to what are sometimes stated as national aspirations or an ‘abstract concept’ so long as the competent Legislature passes the provision in accordance with the procedure laid down by the Constitution or a supra-Constitutional instrument. However, in *Wukala Mahaz Barai Tahafuz Dastoor v. Federation of Pakistan*⁵², the Supreme Court of Pakistan began to acknowledge the need to protect constitutional fundamentals. In this case, the Court observed as follows:

‘Our *grundnorms* are derived from our Islamic faith, which is not merely a religion, but it is a way of life. These *grundnorms* are unchangeable and inseparable from our polity. These are epitomised in the ‘Objectives Resolution’ passed by the Constituent Assembly of Pakistan on 7 March 1949, and were incorporated into the first Constitution of the Islamic Republic of Pakistan in 1956 and repeated in the Constitution of 1962. Its basic postulates are that sovereignty belongs to the people. It is based on the principles of democracy, freedom, equality, tolerance, and social justice, as enunciated in Islam, wherein fundamental human rights are respected, and the independence of the judiciary is fully secured. Can it be argued that any adventurer may usurp control of the State power in Pakistan? Can it violate all these norms and create a new norm of its own in derogation of the same? —————
—————It embodies the spirit and the fundamental norms of the constitutional concept of Pakistan.’⁵³

51 Ibid

52 (PLD 1998 SC 1263)

53 Id at 258

The Court, further, observed that:

‘The cornerstone of the State of Pakistan is that sovereignty rests with Allah, and that Pakistan is his delegatee in the matter of the governance of the State. It is therefore natural that the delegatee, or, for that matter, any ruler, single or collective, in Pakistan can never have unlimited power. If the present regime has legitimate credentials, as the learned Attorney-General claims, the doctrine of necessity does not arise. It must rely on its own source of law.’

In Nepal’s constitutional evolution following the abolition of the monarchy, Indian influence is also reflected in the doctrine of the basic structure. In *Rajendra Prasad Dhakal v. Government of Nepal*⁵⁴, the Supreme Court of Nepal, citing Indian jurisprudence, held that certain constitutional principles, such as the rule of law and judicial independence, are beyond the amending power of the Constitution. In drafting the 2015 Constitution of Nepal, debates over unamendable provisions drew heavily on India’s experience with ‘the doctrine of basic structure’. These examples demonstrate that the development of the basic structure doctrine in India has been adopted by other jurisdictions, including Sri Lanka, Kenya, Colombia, Uganda and Israel which recognise the limits of constitutional amendment.

VII. CONCLUSION

Seventy-five years after the Constitution came into force, the basic structure doctrine remains the most enduring judicial innovation of Indian constitutionalism. From its tentative beginnings in *Shankari Prasad* (1951) and especially in *Sajjan Singh* (1965), to its crystallisation in *Kesavananda Bharati* (1973), and subsequent reaffirmations in *Indira Nehru Gandhi* (1975), *Minerva Mills* (1980), *I.R. Coelho* (2007), and the *NJAC* (2015), *Electoral Bond case* (2024), the doctrine has shaped the trajectory of Indian democracy.

Undoubtedly, the doctrine serves several critical functions: 1) Guardian of constitutional identity by preventing Parliament from altering the Constitution’s essential features; 2) Counter-majoritarian safeguard by insulating democracy, secularism, judicial review, and federalism from transient political majorities; and 3) Instrument of constitutional continuity by balancing change with stability in a rapidly evolving society. The global experience demonstrates that constitutional systems often require unamendable principles to safeguard

54 NKP 1993 p. 478 (Supreme Court of Nepal)

democracy. Germany's 'eternity clause,' Bangladesh's adoption of the doctrine, Pakistan's gradual acceptance, and Nepal's reliance on it show that India's experiment has inspired comparative constitutional jurisprudence. In the words of H.R. Khanna, J., whose decisive opinion in *Kesavananda Bharati* preserved the Constitution's soul, - 'Constitutions are not ephemeral enactments designed to meet the passing hour. They are intended to endure for ages to come.'⁵⁵ The doctrine of basic structure ensures that the Indian Constitution is both a living document and an enduring covenant of justice, liberty, equality, and fraternity. Yet, the doctrine is not without controversy. There are genuine concerns. It lacks a textual basis, undermines parliamentary autonomy and promotes judicial overreach.

To sum up the central philosophy of this historic judicial pronouncement, it is pertinent to refer to Ronald Dworkin's *Law's Empire*⁵⁶, wherein his interpretive theory aligns with the normative foundations of the 'basic structure doctrine', and highlights the importance of constitutional fundamental principles:

'We began with a depressing report of the state of the popular argument about how judges should decide cases? In the United States, the argument is most heated and confused when the judges in question are members of the Supreme Court, and the cases at issue involve constitutional questions that test whether Congress, a state, or the President has the legal power to act, or has attempted to do so. The Constitution grants these institutions only limited powers and imposes significant limitations on each. It denies the Senate the power to originate a money bill and denies the Commander-in-Chief the power to quarter soldiers in private houses in peacetime. Other constraints are notoriously abstract. The Fifth Amendment insists that Congress not take life, liberty or property without due process of law; the Eighth outlaws cruel and unusual punishments; and the Fourteenth, which dominated our sample case, *Brown*, requires that no State deny any person the equal protection of the law.'⁵⁷

55 *Supra* Note 22, per Khanna J

56 Ronald Dworkin, *Law's Empire*, First Indian reprint (Harvard University Press, 1986) P 355

57 *Ibid.* He further says that: 'It does not follow as a matter of iron logic that the Supreme Court should have the power to decide when these limits have been transgressed, for the Constitution might have been interpreted as laying down directions to Congress, the President, and state officials, indicating that these officers had both a legal and a moral duty to follow, yet making

Thus, the 'basic structure doctrine' is like a steady 'North Star' in the galaxy of constitutional principles, providing clear guidance to those implementing the Constitution and shaping fundamental constitutional principles. However, the foregoing observations are not intended to suggest that the doctrine of basic structure is so open-ended that it would be readily applied to every constitutional amendment; most other attempts to question constitutional amendments have been disapproved by the Supreme Court⁵⁸, even when they involved departures from existing constitutional provisions and the constitutional scheme. Recently, it has become a topic of significant debate. The authors submit that, despite criticisms, the doctrine remains essential for safeguarding constitutional identity amid the rise and fall of majoritarian or coalition governments. The reason for the Supreme Court's minimal interference in constitutional amendments is readily apparent. In the Indian constitutional set-up of parliamentary democracy, although judicial review is an essential feature and thereby an immutable part of the basic structure of the Constitution, the power to amend the Constitution is vested in Parliament under Article 368 is equally an inherent part of the basic structure of the Constitution. Both these powers, of amending the Constitution (by Parliament) and of judicial review (by the Constitutional Court), are subject to their own limitations. The interplay between the Parliament's amending powers and the Constitutional Court's judicial review of such exercises of amending power may appear somewhat complex, but ultimately strengthens the constitutional value of the Separation of Powers. This synergy of separation is the strength of our Constitution.

them their own judges. The Constitution would have served as a backdrop for political arguments among institutions about the limits of their constitutional jurisdiction, rather than as a source of authority for any one institution. Chief Justice John Marshall held that the Court's power and duty to enforce the Constitution follow from the Constitution's own declaration that it is the supreme *law* of the land. Lastly, he further concludes as follows: The capital question, now, is not what power the Court has but how its vast power should be exercised? Should it undertake to enforce the whole Constitution, including those provisions that require almost pure political judgment to interpret? Should it decide, for example, whether the details of some State's own constitutional structure provide the 'republican form of government' the federal Constitution demands, or should it leave that to the judgment of Congress or the State itself? —————

What test should it use to decide which decisions are plainly wrong, or wrong on balance?

58 *Shri Raghunathrao Ganpatrao v. Union of India*, (1993) 1 SCR 480; *M Nagraj v. Union of India*, (2006) Supp 7 SCR 336; *K Krishnamurthy v. Union of India*, (2010) 6 SCR 972; *Glanrock Estates Pvt. Ltd. v. Tamil Nadu*, (2010) 12 SCR 597; *Janhit Abhiyan v. Union of India*, (2022) 14 SCR 1